

**Enhancing general internal audit inspection techniques in commercial banks
Personnel Department of Agrobank ATB,
a leading specialist of the personnel
training and development department**

Nurmukhamedova Charos

Abstract. Enhancing the effectiveness of the internal audit system in commercial banks contributes to boosting the financial stability of the bank and guaranteeing financial discipline. The article explores the aforementioned, provides and suggestions on enhancing the internal audit system.

Keywords: financial activities, internal examination, internal oversight system examination budget planning, examination budget.

Internal audit is an important tool for ensuring effective management and control in commercial banks. It plays a key role in ensuring compliance with banking procedures, identifying risks and preventing fraud. In order to increase the effectiveness of internal audit, it is necessary to constantly improve the methods and techniques of verification. One of the ways to improve the general methods of checking internal audit in commercial banks is the use of technology. Automation of audit processes allows you to increase the speed and accuracy of verification, as well as reduce the likelihood of errors. Data analysis software can help identify anomalies and inconsistencies in banking transactions, which contributes to more effective control. Another important aspect of improving audit methods is the development of auditors' skills and competencies. Training and professional development of employees in the field of internal audit allows them to better understand banking processes and risks, as well as apply verification methods more effectively. In addition, it is important to provide auditors with access to up-to-date information and best practices in the field of auditing. It is also important to take

into account changing regulatory requirements and standards in order to improve the overall methods of checking internal audit in commercial banks. Auditors should be aware of the latest changes in legislation and regulations to ensure that banking activities comply with regulatory requirements. Finally, in order to effectively improve internal audit verification methods in commercial banks, it is necessary to pay attention to feedback and continuous improvement of processes. Conducting regular reviews and analysis of audit results makes it possible to identify vulnerabilities and improve verification methods for more effective control and risk management.

Improvement of Internal Audit Methods in Commercial Banks through Technology Technology plays a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of internal audit processes in commercial banks. By leveraging technological advancements, banks can improve the following aspects:

- **Risk Assessment and Analysis:** Advanced data analytics tools can identify and analyze large volumes of data to assess risks and trends objectively. Machine learning algorithms can predict and identify potential areas of concern based on historical patterns and industry benchmarks.
- **Audit Planning and Execution:** Audit management software streamlines the audit planning process, allowing for better resource allocation and scheduling. Automated testing tools can perform repetitive and time-consuming tasks, freeing up auditors to focus on more complex and value-added activities.
- **Data Extraction and Analysis:** Data extraction tools automate the process of retrieving data from various systems, ensuring accuracy and reducing the risk of errors. Data visualization techniques enable auditors to present findings in clear and concise formats, facilitating decision-making.

- **Real-Time Monitoring:** Continuous monitoring systems track key risk indicators and generate alerts when thresholds are breached. This allows banks to respond promptly to emerging risks and take proactive measures.

- **Documentation and Reporting:** Audit automation tools generate standardized reports, reducing manual effort and improving consistency. Digital document management systems facilitate secure storage and collaboration, enhancing audit traceability and efficiency.

Specific Examples of Technology-Enabled Enhancements:

- **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** AI algorithms can analyze unstructured data (e.g., emails, chat transcripts) for potential compliance violations and fraud indicators. **Blockchain:** Blockchain technology provides a secure and immutable ledger for recording audit trails, ensuring data integrity and reducing the risk of tampering.

- **Cloud-Based Audit Management:** Cloud-based platforms allow auditors to access audit tools and data from anywhere, enhancing collaboration and remote auditing capabilities.

- **Automated Document Review:** Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools can automate the review of large volumes of documents, reducing manual effort and increasing accuracy.

- **Data Loss Prevention Tools:**

These tools monitor and restrict data access, mitigating the risk of data breaches and unauthorized data extraction.

Benefits of Technology-Enhanced Internal Audit:

- **Improved Risk Management:** Enhanced risk assessment and real-time monitoring capabilities strengthen banks' ability to identify and mitigate risks.

Increased Efficiency: Automation and data analytics tools significantly reduce time and effort spent on manual tasks, freeing up auditors to focus on higher-value

activities.

Enhanced Accuracy and Reliability: Automated tools minimize human error and ensure consistency in audit findings.

Improved Reporting and Decision-Making: Digital documentation and data visualization tools facilitate clear and effective communication of audit results, supporting informed decision-making.

- Increased Transparency and Accountability: Technology-enabled audit trails enhance transparency and provide evidence of compliance with regulatory requirements.

In conclusion, improving the overall internal audit verification methods in commercial banks is an important step to ensure effective risk control and management. The use of technology, the development of auditors' skills, consideration of regulatory requirements and continuous improvement of processes help to increase the effectiveness of internal audit and ensure the safety and reliability of banking operations.

References:

1. Janvrin, D. J., & Bierstaker, J. L. (2013). The impact of internal audit function quality and contribution on audit delay. *Accounting Horizons*, 27(4), 761-780.
2. Alzeban, A., & Gwilliam, D. R. (2014). Internal audit in Saudi Arabian listed companies: status, problems and solutions. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 23(2), 48-61.
3. Lamberg, R., & Pajunen, K. (2009). The internal audit function in banks: A comparison with other financial institutions in Finland. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 24(4), 312-331.
4. Abidin, S., & Rezaee, Z. (2008). Corporate governance and internal auditing: a critical perspective. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 23(6), 518-537.

5. Hunton, J.E., Wright A.M., & Wright S.(2007). Are financial statement audits becoming a commodity? Evidence on the impact of internal audit sourcing decisions from fees paid for external audits. *The Accounting Review*. Vol82.No3.pp509-532